

Apple Written Communication

Apple Inc. is a company that is recognized around the world for its innovative products and modern technology. It is a company that designs media devices, personal computers, music players, software services, digital content, apps, etc. (Apple Inc., 2016). The company sells its products worldwide through stores, online stores, cellular carriers, etc. For this reason, this company uses rhetorical tools throughout their slogan, website, advertisements, and use of the *i* prefix, to create a connection between people and products, focus on the target audiences, and influence the audience's buying habits. Their written communication is very simple, but it contains powerful messages that persuade people to buy the products.

The Apple slogan "Think Different" was created in 1997 and it had a campaign with an ad that focused on "The crazy ones" or the ones that "think different." (Think Different, 1997). People identify with this concept because most of them, at least once in a while, have felt different from others in the group. By using terms that often are seen as negative such as "crazy", "rebel", "different", people who are labeled with these terms and feel proud of them find a connection with the products. The commercial features famous people such as Nelson Mandela, Bob Dylan, Mahatma Gandhi, Martin Luther King, Pablo Picasso, and others (Apple, 1997). Therefore, it also uses an ethos that appeals to credibility because of the quotes and famous people who were labelled once as different. Consequently, by using emotion and credibility, Apple creates connections between people and their products.

The advertisements and websites use a lot of keywords and catchy phrases in order to capture the attention of the audience. Most of the target audiences are young people, teenagers,

young adults (millennials), and business people. As a result, this modern generation finds the simple and memorable vocabulary attractive. One of the ads uses the phrase “even better” which reflects the quality of the product by using only two words (Apple Inc., 2016). This simple use of the language is a clear example of logos that appeals to logic and persuades people to think that apple products are a smart investment. This is also a clear example of the use of pathos, that appeals to the emotions by creating in a customer’s feelings, needs, and desires to have that specific product. In order to focus on the target audience Apple appeals to the logic and emotions of the consumers.

The *i* prefix is a creative, rhetorical approach to using written communication. Through the *i* prefix before words such as iPad, iPhone, iMac, ibend, iTunes, iCloud, etc. The company’s brand differentiates their products from products of other companies and uses rhetoric in an innovative way. Through this prefix, people from different countries recognize the brand and the products. When someone sees iCloud, he/she relates it with a product or the company. In some cases, the logic of the people is *that it is* an equivalent to Apple Inc., iTunes, iPhone, etc. It also appeals to the emotions of the people because it is trendy and stylish to have *its products*. For people who use this brand it is very common to see apps, products with the *i*. Therefore, it creates interest and attraction for future consumers and people who are not consumers of the product. Apple uses these rhetorical tools to place the products that Apple makes into the people’s mind and influence the audience's buying habits.

In conclusion, Apple Inc. has done an amazing job using its written communication because their message is clear and direct. Through the use of rhetorical tools, they persuade and

motivate their audience to purchase its products. In the consumer's perspective the message is simple but very influential. Throughout the slogan, web site, advertisement, and "i" prefix create connection between people and the products, focus on the target audience, and place the products in people's mind. In order to appeal to different generations, cultures, and backgrounds the company uses simple language to convince them to believe that Apple is striving to make things more advanced and better, by using the use of pathos, logos, ethos appeal.

References

Apple Inc. (1997). Think Different [YouTube video]. Retrieved from <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nmwXdGm89Tk>

Apple Inc. (2016). [Apple website]. Retrieved from <http://www.apple.com/>